

355. Retrospective observational study on the long-term safety of Rituximab in ANCA associated Vasculitis (RIVAS)

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Background/Objectives: To assess the long-term safety of rituximab in a retrospective, secondary use-of-data study in patients with Granulomatosis with Polyangiitis (GPA) and Microscopic Polyangiitis (MPA) by (a) estimating the incidence of serious adverse events (SAEs) and (b) comparing those incidence rates between a rituximab-treated cohort and a control cohort treated with other available therapies.

Methods: Patients in both cohorts were followed by review of their medical records from baseline to study end (30 Sept 2018): baseline was defined by the date of first rituximab treatment since 2003 (rituximab cohort) and time of first disease flare/diagnosis since 2003 (controls). Details of all documented SAEs and adverse events of specific interest including infusion related events, hypogammaglobulinemia or neutropenia were recorded every 12-18 months. Primary endpoint (time to first SAE) is presented along with composite endpoints and repeated event analysis using survival models and regression analyses.

Results: Overall, 392 patients (77% with GPA and 23% with MPA) were included in the study (247 rituximab-exposed patients, 145 control patients) with a total of 2,217 patient years (PY, mean study duration 5.7 years). The study population was 52% female and 93% white-British, with a mean $\pm$ SD age of 60.9 ± 16.3 years. Rituximab patients received a mean of 7.2 infusion doses (ranging from 1 to 23). Significant baseline imbalances between the two cohorts were found. The rituximab cohort had greater levels of comorbidities, a more complex medication history and longer mean disease duration $\pm$ SD at baseline: 54.7 months $\pm$ 70.9 compared to 33.2 months $\pm$ 63.8 (control). A total of 557 events occurred in 164 patients of the rituximab cohort (66.4%) and 185 events in 78 control patients (53.8%). Cohort imbalances will be accounted for by covariate analysis. Estimated incidence rates for infections, cardiovascular events and malignancies will be presented by cohort.

Conclusions: With a long follow-up period and control cohort comparison, the findings of the RIVAS study will provide a good indication on long-term safety of Rituximab in patients with Granulomatosis with Polyangiitis (GPA) and Microscopic Polyangiitis (MPA).

Disclosures: David Jayne's disclosures of commercial conflicts for companies with marketed products for 2021 are: Astra-Zeneca, Aurinia, B, Boehringer-Ingelheim, GSK, Janssen, Novartis, Roche/Genentech, Takeda & Vifor. The RIVAS study was funded by Hoffmann la Roche. We also acknowledge Simon Bond & Marianna Nodale of Cambridge Clinical Trials Unit.